

The role of Rydberg states in Photoionization of NO_2 and $(\text{NO}^+, \text{O}^-)$ Ion Pair Formation induced by One VUV Photon

S. Marggi Poullain¹, K. Veyrinas¹, P. Billaud¹, M. Lebech², Y. J. Picard¹, R. R. Lucchese³ and D. Doweck¹

¹*Institut des Sciences Moléculaires d'Orsay (UMR 8214 Université Paris-Sud et CNRS), Bat. 210-350, Université Paris Sud, F-91405 Orsay Cedex, France*

²*Niels Bohr Institute, DK-2100 Copenhagen, Denmark*

³*Department of Chemistry, Texas A&M University, College Station, Texas 77843, USA*

ABSTRACT

We report a combined experimental and theoretical study of photoionization (PI) of the NO_2 molecule into the NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g^+$) ground state and the photodissociation of NO_2 into the $\text{NO}^+(^1\Sigma^+) + \text{O}^-(^2P)$ ion pair. These processes were induced by 10.9 eV-13 eV synchrotron radiation and the products detected using electron-ion or O^- - NO^+ coincident momentum spectroscopy. The results demonstrate the strong influence of $[\text{R}^*(4b_2)^{-1}, n\alpha_i, \nu_2']$ Rydberg states vibrationally resolved in the ν_2' bending modes for both processes. In particular we emphasize two regions around 11.5 eV and 12.5 eV that were studied in more detail for their relevance to 400 nm multiphoton ionization induced by femtosecond pulses. The photoelectron energy spectra and asymmetry parameters support the existence of two PI mechanisms, as probed with the help of fixed-nuclei frozen-core Hartree-Fock calculations. We found significant deviations from Franck-Condon ionization predictions which may be assigned to vibronic coupling of NO_2^* states such as that induced by a conical intersection. The limited agreement between theory and experiment, even for the non-resonant processes, indicates the need for calculations that go beyond the approximations used in the current study. Ion pair formation leads to strong vibrational and rotational excitation of the $\text{NO}^+(^1\Sigma^+, \nu)$ product, with an ion fragment angular anisotropy depending on both the ν_2' bending

quantum number of the parent molecule and the ν vibrational level of the fragment.

I. INTRODUCTION

The photodynamics of the NO₂ molecule attracts much interest. It is a prototypical model of vibronic coupling and more generally of electron and nuclear coupled dynamics at play in photoexcited molecular states (see e.g. I. Wilkinson and B. J. Whitaker¹ and ref. therein for a recent review). NO₂ has a bent geometry with C_{2v} symmetry in its ground electronic state NO₂ (X ²A₁) (4a₁)² (3b₂)² (1b₁)² (5a₁)² (1a₂)² (4b₂)² (6a₁)¹. The open-valence-shell electronic configuration of the NO₂ radical is at the origin of its complex spectroscopy. The ultrafast photo induced dynamics of NO₂ have been studied using femtosecond time-resolved pump-probe studies combined with energy and/or angle resolved photoelectron and photoion spectroscopy^{2,3}, and with electron-ion momentum spectroscopy that provides molecular frame photoemission patterns^{4,5}. These studies have assigned multiphoton dissociation pathways and highlighted the potential role of non-adiabatic dynamics such as that induced at the conical intersection between the NO₂ (X ²A₁, (4b₂)² (6a₁)¹) ground state and the NO₂ (A ²B₂, (4b₂)¹ (6a₁)²) first excited state that can be reached by absorption of one 400 nm photon. Time-dependent simulations of related quantum wave packet (WP) dynamics aiming at the description of electronic-nuclear coupled dynamics have been developed to support the interpretation of such detailed observables⁶. Recent experimental studies probing such WP dynamics have taken advantage of time resolved high-order harmonic spectroscopy^{7,8}.

In a previous investigation of multiphoton ionization and dissociation of NO₂ induced by femtosecond laser pulses at wavelengths around 400 nm we observed the remarkable production of the (NO⁺, O⁻) ion pair channel amounting to about 15 % of the ionization process⁹. Using the vector correlation (VC) method^{10,11}, we characterized several energetic and angular features of the ion pair dissociation process induced by absorption of four 400 nm photons, corresponding to 12.4-12.6 eV excitation energies. Reaction pathways leading to ion pair formation discussed in ref. 9 support the involvement of intermediate excited states where the valence electronic configuration is strongly mixed with that of Rydberg states. Such mixing occurs with the 3pσ (B₂) lowest member of the R*[(6a₁)⁻¹] Rydberg series converging to NO₂⁺ (X ¹Σ_g⁺) ground state which can be reached by three

photon excitation, or that of the $R^*[(4b_2)^{-1}]$ series, after absorption of the fourth photon. Other remarkable features found for multiphoton induced dissociative and non-dissociative ionization, to be reported in another publication, also motivated a detailed investigation of the dynamics induced by one UV photon excitation in the 12.4-12.6 eV excitation region, corresponding to $4x \sim 400$ nm photon absorption, as well as in the 15.4-15.6 eV region, corresponding to $5x \sim 400$ nm photon absorption, in order to unravel the role assigned to electronic/nuclear dynamics taking place in these two regions from that of molecular dynamics which may be induced by resonant excitation of NO_2 intermediate electronic states after absorption of 1, 2 or 3 ~ 400 nm photons.

After absorption of a single UV photon in the 12.4-12.6 eV excitation region, only two reactions lead to the production of ionized fragments, namely non-dissociative photoionization (PI) of NO_2 :

and ion pair formation

first observed through the O^- production channel by Kratzat *et al.*¹² representing about 0.5 %^{12, 13} of the ionic flux. When comparing the outcome of both multiphoton and one-photon excitation modes, dipole selection rules must be considered, the symmetry of the final state depending on the parity of the number of absorbed photons. However, as it will be discussed later, both changes in the NO_2 geometry and excitation of Rydberg states can occur, which may relax the role of strict selection rules. For the study reported here, we extended the explored region to the 10.915 eV - 13.09 eV excitation energy range. The lowest limit 10.915 (10.937) eV is the ($\text{NO}^+ X^1\Sigma^+ v=0$, $\text{O}^- ^2P_{3/2 (1/2)}$) ion pair energy threshold, whereas 13.09 eV corresponds to the excitation of the $\text{NO}_2^+ (a^3B_2, v_2=3)$ lowest electronically excited state of the molecular ion in the Franck-Condon (FC) region, which has a dissociative branching ratio of the order of 0.6^{14, 15} and may be considered as the vertical threshold for (NO^+ , O , e) dissociative photoionization (DPI) from the NO_2 ground state.

The paper is organized as follows. In Sec. II, we give a brief description of the experimental setup which includes the double velocity spectrometer allowing the (\mathbf{V}_{NO^+} , \mathbf{V}_{O^-}) and ($\mathbf{V}_{\text{NO}_2^+}$, \mathbf{V}_e) vector

correlation study of the ion pair and non-dissociative ionization and the use of VUV synchrotron radiation at SOLEIL. In Sec. III, the ion yield spectra recorded in the 11 – 13 eV range allowing the identification of Rydberg states involved in both reactions are presented. For chosen excitation energies, on resonance or off resonance with a Rydberg state identified in the yield spectra, we carried out VC measurements for both reactions. In Sec. IV, we present the results on the non dissociative ionization in terms of photoelectron spectra and photoelectron angular distributions. In Sec. V, the $(\text{NO}^+, \text{O}^-)$ ion pair formation is discussed by analyzing the kinetic energy release (KER) spectra and the ion fragment angular distributions. Finally, we discuss in the conclusion the contribution of this one photon study to the understanding of electron-nuclear dynamics induced by photoexcitation of the NO_2 molecule.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The (NO_2^+, e) and $(\text{NO}^+, \text{O}^-)$ events were recorded using the VC method^{10, 11}. The double velocity spectrometer¹¹ was installed in the SAPHIRS setup¹⁶ producing a supersonic expansion (nozzle and skimmer diameter: 70 μm and 1mm, respectively). The continuous molecular beam (5% NO_2 in He, backing pressure of 1.5 bar) corresponds typically to a beam diameter of 2-3 mm at the interaction region located at the center of the spectrometer defined as the intersection of the supersonic molecular jet of NO_2 with the light beam. Heating the nozzle at about 120 °C enables us to suppress the contribution of the N_2O_4 dimer component formed in the molecular expansion⁹.

The experiments were carried out on the VUV DESIRS beamline¹⁷ at the SOLEIL synchrotron radiation (SR) facility operated in the single-bunch mode (period: 1.18 μs , pulse time full width at half maximum, FWHM \approx 40 ps). The dimensions of the interaction region are governed by the molecular beam diameter along the light propagation direction (y) and the dimensions of the light beam at the focus point of the order of 200 μm in the horizontal direction (x). Along the vertical direction (z), the dimension varied between 50 and 200 μm depending on the size of the F exit slit of the monochromator. The DESIRS beamline is equipped with a gas filter¹⁸ which was filled with

Ar during these measurements, filtering out the contribution of higher orders transmitted by the grating.

Positively and negatively charged particles are extracted from the interaction region by a dc uniform electric field and guided towards two time-and-position-sensitive RoentDek delay line anode detectors (PSDs) through an intermediate region where two focusing electrostatic lens sets (Λ_+ and Λ_-) are applied¹¹, such that a 4π collection of both particles is achieved. For each coincident event, (NO^+ , O^-) or (NO_2^+ , e), the three components of the emission velocity vectors, (\mathbf{V}_{NO^+} , \mathbf{V}_{O^-}) and ($\mathbf{V}_{\text{NO}_2^+}$, \mathbf{V}_e), respectively, are derived from the time of flight (TOF) and impact position of the particles on their respective PSD. The signal detected on the front MCP of the negatively charged particle detector is used as a common start for (i) an eight channel time-to-digital converter (CTN-TDC, encoding step: 250 ps) with a large multihit capability per channel¹⁹ and (ii) a time-to-amplitude converter (TAC). Four channels of the CTN-TDC are dedicated to the time signals from the ends of the two delay lines of the negatively charged particle detector providing the O^- (or electron) position and the four others to those of the positive ion detector providing the NO^+ (or NO_2^+) position and time of flight as described previously¹¹.

The electronic signal synchronous with the SOLEIL light pulse serves as a stop for the TAC. Two ranges of the TAC have been used in this experiment: a typical 100 ns range is used to record the photoelectron TOF, while a range of 1 μs consistent with the 1.18 μs period of the SR in the single bunch mode provides the O^- TOF distribution with a coding resolution of the order of 100 ps. These conditions permit the use of a low extraction field around 20 V/cm which ensures a complete collection of the O^- ions with a significantly better overall resolution than could be achieved previously using the eight bunch mode⁹. The main instrumental widths contributing to the resolution in the determination of the velocity components for (NO^+ , O^-) and (NO_2^+ , e), and subsequently energies and angles of the emitted charged particles, are the dy length of the interaction region along the light beam axis and the δt jitter of the electron TOF estimated here of the order of $\delta t \approx 170$ ps affecting the velocity vector components V_{ye} , V_{yi} and V_{ze} , respectively.

III. ION YIELD SPECTRA

Figure 1a presents typical (NO_2^+ , e) photoionization and (NO^+ , O⁻) ion pair yield spectra recorded with steps of 10 meV as a function of the incident light energy in the 10.918 eV -13.0 eV range, where both channels are continuously populated. During the energy scan the electromagnetic planar / helicoidal undulator OPHELIE2 was adjusted to follow the grating movement in order to ensure a constant transmission at maximum-intensity of the flux. We used a 200 grooves/mm grating, corresponding to a resolution of 0.072 nm for a 100 μm exit slit. For these scans, the photon excitation energy resolution varied between 7 to 10 meV for the non dissociative photoionization and between 14 meV to 20 meV for the ion pair measurements using outgoing slits F of 100 μm and 200 μm , respectively, except when otherwise mentioned. Resolved structures are observed in both spectra, in particular in two excitation energy regions of interest here: around 11.5 eV and around 12.4 eV that we refer to as regions I and II, respectively. They highlight the excitation of vibrationally resolved bending modes of Rydberg series [$\text{R}^*(4b_2)^{-1}, \nu_2'$] converging to the NO_2^+ ($^3\text{B}_2$) lowest electronically excited state of NO_2^+ , based on the assignment proposed by Morioka *et al.*²⁰ in photoabsorption spectra.

The NO_2^+ ion yield spectrum was recorded previously by Dibeler and coworkers¹³ using mass spectrometry in the 9.54 and 20.66 eV excitation energy range. The partially resolved structures in the 10.78 - 13.77 eV region were attributed to autoionization, without specific assignment. In the excitation energy region I, superimposed onto a continuous component, the (NO_2^+ , e) ion yield spectrum displays well resolved peaks separated by about 80 meV which are attributed to the ($\nu_2' = 0 - 6$) vibrational progression of the $4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ ($^3\text{B}_2$) Rydberg transition based on the assignment of Morioka *et al.*²⁰. In the following we use the notation $4b_2 \rightarrow n\alpha_i$ ($^3\text{B}_2$) to represent an electronic transition from the ($4b_2$) initial orbital into a $n\alpha_i$ Rydberg orbital, where ($\alpha_i \sim a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2$) and e.g., ($^3\text{B}_2$) denotes the symmetry of the NO_2^+ ionic core. We note that other vibrational progressions identified in the photoabsorption spectrum²⁰ corresponding e.g., to $4b_2 \rightarrow 3d\alpha_i$ ($^3\text{B}_2$) in region I, or

$4b_2 \rightarrow 3sa_1$ (1B_2) and $1a_2 \rightarrow 3p\alpha_i$ ($^3,^1A_2$) in the 10.8-11.1 eV energy range are not observed significantly in the ionization channel, also explored at higher photon energy resolution (≤ 5 meV in Figure 1b and 1c, recorded with a 50 μm F slit and steps of 2.5 meV). In the following, for simplicity, we omit the α_i character when more than one symmetry is possible. In the 12.0 - 12.8 eV range, the spectrum shows more complex structures with a lower contrast making the identification difficult. In Fig. 1c which displays an expanded view of the 12.3-12.6 eV range (region II), in similar conditions, the peaks can be assigned to bending vibrational levels of the four transitions to Rydberg states: $4b_2 \rightarrow 5sa_1$, $4b_2 \rightarrow 4d$, $4b_2 \rightarrow 5d$ and $4b_2 \rightarrow 6sa_1$ (3B_2) the latter being the most intense for photoionization; the energy spacing is typically of 10 meV and 15 meV between neighbor Rydberg states such as $5d(v'_2=3)$ and $4d(v'_2=7)$, or $4d(v'_2=7)$ and $6sa_1(v'_2=3)$, respectively. At 12.9 eV, a strong increase in intensity corresponds to the opening of a second pattern of non-dissociative photoionization. The three peaks observed are assigned to direct ionization into the bending vibrational levels of the NO_2^+ (a^3B_2 , $v = 0, 1, 2$) excited state¹⁴.

In region II, the width of the resolved peaks (FWHM) is 5 meV, comparable to the excitation energy resolution in the measurement, compared to about 12 meV in region I. This is an indication of a longer autoionization lifetime for the $4b_2 \rightarrow 5sa_1$, $4b_2 \rightarrow 4d$, $4b_2 \rightarrow 5d$ and $4b_2 \rightarrow 6sa_1$ (3B_2) states in region II, than for the $4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ (3B_2) Rydberg state in region I, where it can be estimated roughly of the order of 30 fs.

The ion pair reaction has been discussed previously by Kratzat *et al.*¹² who reported the O⁻ production yield as a function of the excitation energy in the 10.5 – 15.5 eV range. Above the onset at 10.92 eV assigned to a direct transition to the ion-pair state, their spectrum displayed resolved structures around 11.5 eV attributed to the bending vibrational levels of the $4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ (3B_2) Rydberg series, from $v'_2 = 0$ up to $v'_2 = 6$ with the vibrational spacing $\Delta E_{\text{vib ben}} \approx 80$ meV²⁰. Two peaks of strong relative intensity forming a doublet around 12.45 eV have been associated with excitation of bending vibrational levels in the $4b_2 \rightarrow 4d$ and $5d$ (3B_2) Rydberg series.

In the (NO^+ , O^-) ion pair yield spectrum displayed in Figure 1a the $v'_2 = 0-6$ bending vibrational

levels of the $4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ (3B_2) transition are identified in region I with a better energy resolution than in ref. 12 (see also Fig. 1b), as observed for the photoionization spectrum, with small differences found in the relative intensity of the populated vibrational levels between both reactions. The shoulders visible on the left side of the peaks can be assigned to a contribution of the bending vibrational levels of the $4b_2 \rightarrow 4p$ ($v_2' = 0 - 4$) Rydberg series. Two peaks are observed in region II ($h\nu \approx 12.41$ and 12.48 eV) where the dominant doublet was reported by Kratzat¹², however they are found here of comparable intensity with the rest of the spectrum and in particular with the third peak at 12.55 eV. The broader width of these structures recorded with a spectral resolution of about 18 meV (compared to 5 meV for photoionization) does not allow us to resolve further the contribution of $4b_2 \rightarrow n\alpha_i$ series, however the peak shape indicates the contribution of several $4b_2 \rightarrow 4d, 5d$ or $6s$ transitions.

FIG. 1. (a) Ion yield spectra for (NO_2^+, e) and $(\text{NO}^+, \text{O}^-)$ coincident events as a function of the excitation energy (red plain line, blue bold line respectively) recorded with a step of 10 meV; the x50 scaling factor takes into account the difference in detection efficiency of the O^- ions ($\sim 20\%$) and electrons ($\sim 50\%$)⁹; the spectral resolution ranges between 7 to 10 meV and 14 meV to 20 meV, respectively. The circle labels an argon absorption line at 11.828 eV related with the use of the Ar filter (see text). Expanded view of both yield spectra with improved resolution for (NO_2^+, e) (≈ 5 meV) in: (b) region I between 11.3 eV and 11.85 eV (with a step of 2.5 meV and 10 meV, resp.) and (c) region II between 12.3 eV and 12.6 eV (with a step of 2.5 meV and 5 meV, resp.). In (b), v_2' vibrational level positions of $4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ [$R^*(4b_2)^{-1}, v_2'$] Rydberg states are labeled using ref. 20. In (c) [$R^*(4b_2)^{-1}, v_2'$] Rydberg states are labeled as follows: stars correspond to $4b_2 \rightarrow 6sa_1$ ($v_2' = 0 - 3$), dots to $4b_2 \rightarrow 4d$ ($v_2' = 4 - 7$), triangles to $4b_2 \rightarrow 5d$ ($v_2' = 0 - 3$) and rhombs to $4b_2 \rightarrow 5s\sigma$ ($v_2' = 3, 4$). Red plain arrows label excitation energies selected for VC measurements of (NO_2^+, e) discussed in sections IV and blue bold arrows those of $(\text{NO}^+, \text{O}^-)$ discussed in section V.

In Sec. IV and V we report VC measurements characterizing non-dissociative photoionization leading to NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g^+$) and $(\text{NO}^+, \text{O}^-)$ ion pair formation, respectively. For both reactions we have selected well defined photon excitation energies in the excitation regions I and II, corresponding to the intensity maximum of a vibrationally resolved resonance (labeled as ON resonance) or between

two resonances (OFF resonance) when these are clearly resolved.

IV. PHOTOIONIZATION INTO THE NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g^+$) GROUND STATE

A. Photoelectron energy spectra

Figure 2a represents a typical photoelectron (PE) spectrum obtained in region I, considering first the OFF resonance situation, e.g., at $h\nu = 11.62$ eV, which consists of a broad distribution extending from $E_e \approx 0$ eV to $E_e \approx 1$ eV. The corresponding binding energy region is included in the broad band region associated with the FC overlap of the NO_2 ($X^2A_1, 0,0,0$) ground state with the potential energy surface of $\text{NO}_2^+(X^1\Sigma_g)$ ionic ground state of linear geometry, whose minimum is shifted with respect to that of the bent NO_2 (X^2A_1) neutral state. High resolution photoelectron spectroscopy (PES) at $h\nu = 21.2$ eV¹⁴ revealed that the photoelectron band contains closely lying vibrational lines with a spacing of 25 meV, much narrower than the 77 meV spacing predicted for the ν_2 bending vibration, the two stretching modes leading to larger values (~ 175 meV for ν_1 and ~ 296 meV for ν_3). These long vibrational progressions have been further characterized in high-resolution threshold photoionization spectroscopy using a PFI-ZEKE technique²¹, involving Fermi resonances between symmetric stretch and bend. The 25 meV structure assigned to combination bands of the ν_1 and ν_2 modes is not resolved in the present conditions. Using Monte Carlo (MC) simulations of the electron trajectories in the VC spectrometer the resolution is estimated to be about $\delta E_e \approx 60$ meV for $E_e \approx 0.2$ eV, operating with a 15 V/cm extraction field. The shape of the presently reported PE spectrum is comparable to the FC distribution estimated from PES at 21.2 eV¹⁴ for photoelectron energies $E_e \geq 0.5$ eV, where $E_e \approx 0.5$ eV corresponds to the $E_B^{(\text{FC})} \approx 11.2$ eV binding energy at the center of the FC region. However, in the 0-0.5 eV lower E_e part of the spectrum the profile deviates from the FC distribution, with a higher relative intensity and three partially resolved structures with a spacing of about 160 meV close to that of the ν_1 symmetric stretching vibration. We note that since ion pair and photoionization channels are both populated in this region, OFF-resonance ionization can include both direct ionization and indirect ionization *via*

a neutral state, such as the ion pair state. When the photon excitation energy is chosen ON-resonance with one of the most populated vibrational levels of the NO_2 $4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ (3B_2) [$R^*(4b_2)^{-1}, \nu_2'$] Rydberg series, e.g., $\nu_2' = 4$ at $h\nu = 11.66$ eV, the ionization probability increases by a factor of about 2.3 (see Fig. 1a). Additionally, the shape of the PE spectrum remains quite similar to that of the OFF resonance case, with weakly resolved structures pointing to similar ν_1 vibrational states. This indicates that the autoionization channel considered here ionizes into the $\text{NO}_2^+(X \ ^1\Sigma_g)$ ground state, with the same probability as observed OFF resonance, suggesting the role of stretching modes for binding energies higher than $E_B^{(\text{FC})} \approx 11.2$ eV. Note that the PE spectra ON/OFF are normalized in each figure consistent with the measured ion yield.

FIG. 2. Photoelectron spectra of the (NO_2^+, e) coincident events measured for: (a) $h\nu = 11.66$ eV (purple dotted line, ON resonance with $4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ (3B_2) Rydberg state) and $h\nu = 11.62$ eV (blue full line, OFF resonance), with an extraction field $E_{\text{ext}} = 15$ V/cm ensuring a 4π collection of electrons up to $E_e = 1.3$ eV;

(b) $h\nu = 12.39$ eV (cyan dashed line, ON $4b_2 \rightarrow 5d$ (3B_2)), $h\nu = 12.41$ eV (purple dotted line, ON $4b_2 \rightarrow 6s$ (3B_2)) and $h\nu = 12.44$ eV (blue full line, OFF), with $E_{\text{ext}} = 25$ V/cm (4π collection for $E_e \leq 2$ eV); (c) $h\nu = 12.56$ eV (cyan dashed line, ON $4b_2 \rightarrow 4d$ (3B_2)), $h\nu = 12.57$ eV (purple dotted line, ON $4b_2 \rightarrow 6sa_1$ (3B_2)) and $h\nu = 12.59$ eV (blue full line, OFF) with $E_{\text{ext}} = 25$ V/cm. The PE spectra ON/OFF are normalized in each figure consistently with the measured ion yield. The dash-dotted lines feature FC profiles estimated from PES in Baltzer *et al*¹¹ in the binding energy range $10.4 \leq E_B \leq 12.2$ eV. The maximum of the FC region at $E_B \approx 11.2$ eV corresponds to $E_{e\text{-FC}} \approx 0.4$ eV, $E_{e\text{-FC}} \approx 1.2$ eV and $E_{e\text{-FC}} \approx 1.4$ eV in (a), (b) and (c) respectively, and the amplitudes are adjusted such that a good fit is obtained on the high E_e side of each spectrum. (A) and (B) label the two peaks of the PE spectrum in region II as discussed in section IV.

Figure 2b displays the PE spectra measured for three excitation energies in region II, namely at $h\nu \approx 12.39$ eV (ON resonance with $4b_2 \rightarrow 5d$ (3B_2) $v_2' = 1$ Rydberg state), $h\nu \approx 12.41$ eV (ON resonance with $4b_2 \rightarrow 6sa_1$ (3B_2) $v_2' = 1$ Rydberg state) and $h\nu \approx 12.44$ eV (OFF resonance) with a 25 V/cm extraction field. The F slit (40 μm width) enables selective excitation of the closely spaced resonant states. In this region the ionization probability increases by a smaller factor than in region I. When the photon energy is ON resonance, it increases by a factor of 1.3 or 1.15 for excitation of the $6sa_1$ or $5d$ state, respectively. Typical PE energy resolutions estimated through the MC simulations are of the order of $\delta E_e \approx 80$ meV/200 meV for $E_e \approx 0.2$ eV/1.2 eV, respectively. The PE spectra (Fig. 2b) show the broad peak (A), $0.4 \text{ eV} \leq E_e \leq 1.5 \text{ eV}$, which reflects ionization into the NO_2^+ ($X \ ^1\Sigma_g^+$) state in the limits of the FC region of the NO_2 ($X \ ^2A_1$) state. An additional peak (B), however, is observed at threshold electron energies with a remarkable increase ON resonance. For excitation of the $5d$ (3B_2) $v_2' = 1$ Rydberg state, the ionization enhancement leads selectively to low energy electrons (peak b, $0 \text{ eV} \leq E_e \leq 0.5 \text{ eV}$), while, for excitation of the $6sa_1$ (3B_2) $v_2' = 1$ Rydberg state, photoelectrons are also observed up to the FC maximum of peak (A) at $E_e \approx 1.2$ eV.

A similar behavior is observed for the set of PE spectra (Fig. 2c) recorded at $h\nu = 12.56$ eV (ON resonance with $4b_2 \rightarrow 4d$ (3B_2) $v_2' = 7$ Rydberg state), $h\nu = 12.57$ eV (ON resonance with

$4b_2 \rightarrow 6sa_1$ (3B_2 $v_2' = 3$ Rydberg state) and $h\nu = 12.59$ eV (OFF resonance), although in this latter case the enhancement of the ionization probability ON resonance, in particular for the $6sa_1$ (3B_2 $v_2' = 3$ state, is more equally shared between both peaks (B) and (A) than at lower photon energy.

B. Photoelectron angular distributions

The (E_e, θ_e) bidimensional histogram (Figure 3) displays the correlation between the photoelectron energy and its emission polar angle with respect to the VUV light polarization axis, for the (NO_2^+, e) coincident events, for a photon energy of $h\nu \approx 12.39$ eV (region II, ON resonance with $4b_2 \rightarrow 5d$ (3B_2) $v_2' = 1$ Rydberg state). The projection of the (E_e, θ_e) histogram onto the horizontal axis is identical to the electron energy spectrum at the same photon energy included in Figure 2b. The projection onto the vertical axis leads to the photoelectron angular distribution (PAD) characterized by the β_e asymmetry parameter, which can be obtained for each identified process in the energy spectrum. For the vertical band selection at $0.4 \text{ eV} \leq E_e \leq 1.5 \text{ eV}$ associated with peak (A) in the photoelectron energy spectrum, one observes a preferred electron emission for polar angles around 0° and 180° , parallel to the polarization axis, associated with a positive β_e value. For the narrow band associated with peak (B) at threshold electron energies, the emission is almost isotropic, corresponding to small β_e values. A detailed evolution of the asymmetry parameter β_e as a function of the photoelectron energy is obtained using a fitting procedure of the (E_e, θ_e) histogram. Figure 4 displays this evolution for the eight excitation energies considered in Sec IVA. In region I, the result for a measurement at 11.62 eV (OFF resonance) shows a strong increase from $\beta_e \approx 0.9$ at $E_e = 0.1$ eV up to $\beta_e \approx 1.4$ at $E_e = 0.4$ eV, which corresponds to the $E_B^{(FC)} \approx 11.2$ eV binding energy at the center of the FC region, and then a slow decrease when the electron energy is above 0.4 eV. MC simulations of the kinematics of this process show that the smaller values of β_e observed for low electron energies are beyond the expected reduction of the angular resolution with decreasing E_e . When the excitation energy is on resonance ($h\nu = 11.66$ eV), the $\beta_e(E_e)$ curve is of similar shape, however the β_e values increasing from 0.50 to 0.9 are significantly lower for all E_e energies. This

behavior confirms that autoionization of the $4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ (3B_2) [$R^*(4b_2)^{-1}, v_2'$] Rydberg state contributes to the whole PE spectrum. We note that smooth oscillations of the β_e parameter are also observed in the $E_e = 0-0.5$ eV region with a similar period of the order of 160 meV as found in the PE spectrum.

FIG. 3. (E_e, θ_e) bidimensional diagram of the (NO_2^+, e) coincident events for an excitation energy of 12.39 eV and an extraction field of 25V/cm. The intensity scale runs from white (lowest intensity) to black (highest intensity) in linear scale, as shown. The contour lines are spaced by 10% of the maximum value.

As previously observed analyzing the PE energy spectra, the situation in region II presents similarities and differences with region I. The similarity is highlighted when the asymmetry parameters are plotted as a function of the binding energy E_B (not shown), the β_e curve displaying a comparable slow increase for $10.5 \text{ eV} \leq E_B \leq 11.25 \text{ eV}$ followed by a strong decrease for $E_B \geq 11.25 \text{ eV}$ for both regions I and II. This behavior is reflected in Figure 4 for different excitation energies in region II displaying an increase of β_e from 0.3 at $E_e \approx 0.5 \text{ eV}$ up to $\beta_e \approx 1.0$ at $E_e^{(FC)}$, followed by a slow decrease for E_e values larger than $E_e^{(FC)}$. The shape of the β_e variation with E_e or E_B is very similar for OFF (12.44 eV) and ON resonance (12.39 and 12.41 eV) as observed in region I, however the emission anisotropies remain comparable in region II whereas a significant decrease of β_e was found ON resonance in region I. This stronger influence of the ON/OFF

character in region I in terms of β_e can be partially attributed to the higher amplification of the ionization probability ON resonance in this region as compared to region II. Finally a third E_e or E_B region is identified in region II: at the lowest E_e ($E_e \leq 0.4$ eV) values corresponding to the threshold photoelectron peak (B), β_e remains of the order of 0.2-0.3 with a rather flat variation with E_e and a weak dependence for the different OFF and ON excitation energies. Similar tendencies in terms of β_e dependences with E_e or E_B are found for excitation energies ON and OFF resonance around 12.57 eV.

FIG. 4. Evolution of the asymmetry parameter β_e as a function of the photoelectron energy E_e for the (NO_2^+ , e) coincident events recorded in region I: at $h\nu = 11.66$ eV (red bold dashed line, ON resonance $4s a_1$ (3B_2) $v_2' = 4$) and $h\nu = 11.62$ eV (red bold full line, OFF resonance) with $E_{\text{ext}} = 15$ V/cm, and in region II: at $h\nu = 12.39$ eV (dashed black line, ON resonance $5d$ (3B_2) $v_2' = 1$ Rydberg state), $h\nu = 12.41$ eV (dotted black line, ON resonance $6s a_1$ (3B_2) $v_2' = 3$) and $h\nu = 12.44$ eV (full black line, OFF resonance), and at $h\nu = 12.56$ eV (dashed grey line, ON resonance $4d$ (3B_2) $v_2' = 7$), $h\nu = 12.57$ eV (dotted grey line, ON resonance $6s a_1$ (3B_2) $v_2' = 3$) and $h\nu = 12.59$ eV (full grey line, OFF resonance) with $E_{\text{ext}} = 25$ V/cm. Statistical error bars, not shown for clarity, are between 0.01 and 0.02. The blue full line (triangles) features the result of the calculation described in the text.

Vertical arrows at $E_{e\text{-FC}} \approx 0.4$ eV (region I), $E_{e\text{-FC}} \approx 1.2$ eV and $E_{e\text{-FC}} \approx 1.4$ eV (region II), correspond to the

center of the FC region for the three excitation energies, respectively. The bandwidth of the fit is 150 meV with a step of 15 meV except for measurements at $h\nu = 11.62$ eV and $h\nu = 11.66$ eV for which the bandwidth is 70 meV and the step is 5 meV.

The β_e asymmetry parameter for direct ionization from the NO_2 (X^2A_1) ground state at the equilibrium geometry ($R(\text{N-O}) = 1.19455$ Å and $\angle\text{ONO} = 133.85^\circ$)²² into the NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g^+$) ionic state, assuming the same geometry, has been calculated as a function of the excitation energy using a Frozen-Core Hartree-Fock (FCHF) method and the ePolyScat code^{23,24}. The single-center expansions included partial waves up to $l_{\text{max}} = 60$. The basis set used to describe the orbitals was the augmented correlation consistent polarized valence triple zeta (aug-cc-pVTZ) basis set^{25,26}. The result of this calculation included in Fig. 4 is compared with the measured β_e dependence for OFF resonance ionization at $h\nu = 11.62$ eV (region I), $h\nu = 12.44$ eV and $h\nu = 12.59$ eV (region II). For both energy ranges, the calculation describes quite well the experimental result for electron energies above the $E_e^{(\text{FC})}$ value corresponding to the center of the FC region ($E_e^{(\text{FC})} \approx 0.4$ eV at $h\nu = 11.62$ eV, $E_e^{(\text{FC})} \approx 1.2$ eV at $h\nu = 12.44$ eV and $E_e^{(\text{FC})} \approx 1.4$ eV at $h\nu = 12.59$ eV), i.e., a slow decrease of β_e with increasing E_e values. However, the significant decrease of β_e with decreasing E_e values measured for electron energies below the $E_e^{(\text{FC})}$ values ($0 \leq E_e \leq 0.4$ eV, and $0.4 \leq E_e \leq 1.2$ eV, respectively, in regions I and II) is not predicted by the FCHF calculation describing direct ionization, as further discussed in the next section.

C. Photoionization mechanisms

The characteristics reported in Sec. IVA and IVB for photoionization in the explored regions I and II point to different ionization mechanisms. A common feature to all photon excitation energies is that the shape of the PE spectra for E_e energies larger than $E_e^{(\text{FC})}$, or for binding energies $E_B^{(\text{FC})} \leq 11.2$ eV, is comparable to the FC distribution observed in PES¹⁴. In this E_e region, for photon energies OFF resonance, the magnitude of the β_e asymmetry parameter and its variation with E_e are

consistent with those predicted by the FCHF calculations for direct ionization into the NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g$) ground state, at the equilibrium geometry.

For higher binding energies $E_B^{(\text{FC})} \geq 11.2$ eV, on the one hand the shape of the PE spectra in region I deviates from the FC distribution for all photon excitation energies, with an enhancement of the intensity and partial resolution of structures separated by about 160 meV, whereas in region II the PE spectra OFF resonance is consistent with the FC distribution. On the other hand, for both regions I and II, the β_e parameter strongly decreases with decreasing E_e , a dependence which is not described by the FCHF calculation. These observations can be understood as a splitting of the photoexcited population. For the low binding energy component ($E_B^{(\text{FC})} \leq 11.2$ eV), OFF resonance excitation behaves like a direct ionization process at the equilibrium geometry. For the higher component ($E_B^{(\text{FC})} \geq 11.2$ eV), the observed features suggest that an additional process such as a rapid change in geometry, a vibronic coupling or resonant ionization of a neutral excited state takes place, which strongly influences the photoionization outcome²⁷.

In addition, one can distinguish two autoionization mechanisms in regions I and II labeled processes “1” and “2” in Figure 5 which displays a schematic representation of potential energy curves standing for the NO_2 (X^2A_1), NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g$), NO_2^+ (a^3B_2) states including a potential curve leading to (NO^+ , O^-) ion pair formation. Autoionization of the $4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ (3B_2) [$R^*(4b_2)^{-1}$, ν_2] Rydberg states in region I (process “1”) strongly increases the ionization yield for all E_e energies and preserves the shape of the PE spectrum, while in the second mechanism, enhanced in particular for excitation of Rydberg series of d character in region II, quasi-resonant autoionization populates highly vibrationally excited states of NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g$) outside the limits of the FC region at $\angle\text{ONO}$ angles θ smaller than the equilibrium angle $\theta_{\text{eq}} = 133.85^\circ$.

FIG. 5. Selected cuts at fixed coordinates of relevant computed potential energy surfaces as a function of the θ ONO bond angle and the N-O bond length for neutral NO₂ and ionic NO₂⁺ molecular states. X²A₁ denotes the ground state of NO₂ (red bold lines), X¹Σ_g⁺ and a³B₂ the ground and first excited states of NO₂⁺ (purple full and blue dash-dotted lines, respectively). A repulsive potential energy curve leading to the ion pair formation is also sketched at the equilibrium angle θ_{eq} (orange dashed line). The (NO⁺ X¹Σ⁺ v=0, O⁻ ²P_{1/2} or _{3/2}) and (NO⁺ (X¹Σ, v=0) + O (³P) + e) dissociation limits are indicated.

Two mechanisms for NO₂⁺ (X¹Σ_g⁺) formation, 1 and 2, as discussed in the text, are schematized.

Similar characteristics to that of process “2” have been observed in PI of polyatomic molecules and assigned to vibrational or rotational autoionization of highly internally excited Rydberg states of the manifold converging to the ground state of the molecular ion^{28, 29}. In the present study, this process requires coupling between the [R*(4b₂)⁻¹, v₂] Rydberg states and the [R*(6a₁)⁻¹, v] series

converging to the NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g$). According to a model initially proposed by Guyon *et al.*²⁸ and extended by Chupka *et al.*²⁹, such an interaction could be favored by the coupling of both series through intermediate repulsive states. The molecular states correlating to the ion-pair dissociation limits, which are populated channels in this excitation process, might participate in this mediation role. Other decay channels such as dissociation into neutral fragments could also contribute to this process²⁰.

A simpler scheme consisting of a direct coupling between the $[\text{R}^*(4b_2)^{-1}]$ and $[\text{R}^*(6a_1)^{-1}]$ Rydberg states has been investigated here. For this purpose, the geometry dependence of these Rydberg states has been studied by considering that of the corresponding NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g^+$) and (a^3B_2) ion states. We have computed portions of the potential energy surfaces for these two states with an internally contracted multireference configuration interaction (icMRCI) calculation with Davidson correction. The orbitals for the icMRCI calculation were obtained from a state averaged valence complete active space self-consistent field (SA-VCASSCF) calculation using the $X^1\Sigma_g^+$ and a^3B_2 ionic states of NO_2^+ . The one-electron basis set was the augmented correlation consistent polarized valence quadruple zeta (aug-cc-pVQZ) basis set^{25,26}. The calculations were performed using the MOLPRO program³⁰. In Figure 6 we give the potential for these two states as a function of the $\angle\text{ONO}$ angle θ with the N-O bond lengths fixed at 1.19455 Å, which is the equilibrium value for the neutral ground state. The vertical excitation from the ground state occurs at $\theta_{\text{eq}} = 133.85^\circ$. The observed crossing between the ionic states supports the fact that $[\text{R}^*(4b_2)^{-1}]$ Rydberg states will cross the $[\text{R}^*(6a_1)^{-1}]$ Rydberg states at angles around $\theta = 114^\circ$ and that the $[\text{R}^*(4b_2)^{-1}]$ states will have slightly lower energies at that angle compared to their energies at the vertical geometry. Similar features were obtained in ref. 6. Note that the ion states have different spin symmetries, and thus do not interact when spin orbit effects are not included. However, the corresponding Rydberg states that can be excited starting from the initial doublet state will all have doublet spin symmetry and will lead to a series of avoided crossings between states in the $[\text{R}^*(4b_2)^{-1}]$ and $[\text{R}^*(6a_1)^{-1}]$ manifolds. Thus, depending on the coupling of the $[\text{R}^*(4b_2)^{-1}]$ Rydberg states to the autoionization

continuum, some amplitude can be found in the $[R^*(6a_1)^{-1}]$ manifold. In this process “2”, amplitude in the $[R^*(6a_1)^{-1}]$ Rydberg series leads to outgoing flux in NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g, \nu$) vibrationally excited states due to autoionization. The two decay pathways labeled as processes “1” and “2” here are in competition. Broader peaks of the $4b_2 \rightarrow 4s_{a_1}$ (3B_2) Rydberg states in region I are consistent with strong coupling to the autoionization continuum, while narrower linewidths of the $4b_2 \rightarrow 5s_{a_1} / 4d / 5d$ and $6s_{a_1}$ (3B_2) Rydberg states in region II may favor neutral channel decay and coupling through the $[R^*(4b_2)^{-1}]$ series into the $[R^*(6a_1)^{-1}, \nu]$ series, and through autoionization leading to flux in the highly vibrationally excited $e+\text{NO}_2^+$ ($X^1\Sigma_g, \nu$) states (process “2”). This scheme is consistent with the linewidth observations reported in Sec. III. In addition their behavior might also depend on the s or d character of the Rydberg state, or on its bending vibrational level.

FIG. 6. Bending potential for the two lowest ion states of NO_2^+ with the NO bond lengths fixed at their equilibrium value for the neutral ground state of $R_{\text{NO}} = 1.19455 \text{ \AA}$. The vertical line indicates the location of vertical transitions from the ground state.

Turning to the β_e asymmetry parameter, the observed evolution as a function of the E_e photoelectron energy together with the result of the FCHF calculation, suggests that ionization into $\text{NO}_2^+(X^1\Sigma_g, \nu)$ FC region, in a geometry with $\angle\text{ONO}$ angle $\theta > \theta_{\text{eq}}$ ($\theta_{\text{eq}} = 133.85^\circ$), is governed by the photoelectron energy dependence in the direct ionization process. However, since the significant drop in value at lower photoelectron kinetic energy observed experimentally is not seen in the

FCHF calculation at fixed equilibrium geometry of the molecule. We explored the geometry dependence of β_e within the adiabatic FCHF approximation and did not find a satisfactory explanation for the experimentally observed behavior. Thus this behavior must be due to either a breakdown of the adiabatic approximation, i.e. the Born-Oppenheimer approximation, or to neglected correlation effects.

V. ION PAIR (NO^+ , O^-) FORMATION

The $(\mathbf{V}_{\text{NO}^+}, \mathbf{V}_{\text{O}^-})$ vector correlation provides the (KER, χ) bidimensional histogram for the $(\text{NO}^+, \text{O}^-)$ coincident events, correlating the kinetic energy release (KER), i.e. the sum of the kinetic energies of both fragments, to the χ emission polar angle of the fragment ion momentum relative to the light polarization axis. Figure 7 presents this histogram for an experiment performed at $h\nu = 11.66$ eV (ON resonance, $\text{NO}_2 4b_2 \rightarrow 4s_{a_1} (^3B_2) (v_2' = 4)$) with an extraction field of 15 V/cm. The vertical bands of accumulated events resulting into resolved peaks after projection onto the abscissa provide the KER spectrum, while the photofragment angular emission distribution characterized by the asymmetry parameter β_N results from projection onto the ordinate.

FIG. 7. (KER, χ) bidimensional diagram of the $(\text{NO}^+, \text{O}^-)$ coincident events for $h\nu = 11.66$ eV and $E_{\text{ext}} = 15\text{V/cm}$. The intensity scale runs from white (lowest intensity) to black (highest intensity) in linear scale, as shown. The contour lines are spaced by 10% of the maximum value.

A. Kinetic energy release distribution

Figure 8 displays selected KER spectra of the (NO^+ , O^-) ionic fragments obtained OFF and ON resonance, in region I. The main peaks in the KER distribution shown in Fig. 8a for the resonant excitation $4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ (3B_2) ($\nu_2' = 3$) at $h\nu = 11.58$ eV are assigned to the excitation of three resolved vibrational levels of the NO^+ (${}^1\Sigma^+$, $\nu = 0, 1, 2$) molecular fragment with a vibrational spacing about $\Delta E_{\text{vib}} \approx 290$ meV, the O^- ${}^2P_{3/2 \text{ or } 1/2}$ spin-orbit states separated by 22 meV being unresolved. It shows an increase of the probability for ion pair formation when the NO^+ vibrational level increases reflecting a favored energy transfer to the internal degrees of freedom of the fragment rather than to the translational energy of the system, very similar to what was found in the multiphoton ion pair formation⁹ and observed in other ion pair processes previously³¹. The ro-vibrational peaks tentatively fitted by a Gaussian profile of 170 meV (FWHM), larger than the instrumental resolution of the order of 60 meV estimated by MC simulations, indicate a minimum rotational excitation of the NO^+ ion up to $N \sim 25$ (in Hund's case (b) nomenclature)³², above the expected rotational excitation at room temperature (293 K, typically $N \sim 12$). NO^+ rotational excitation is specially enhanced for NO^+ (${}^1\Sigma^+$, $\nu = 1$), which displays two resolved structures assigned to rotational maxima at $N \sim 13$ and $N \sim 30$. Such a bimodal rotational distribution is also observed for $\nu = 1$ ON resonance at $h\nu = 11.50$ eV ($4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ (3B_2), $\nu_2' = 2$). Comparing the KER spectra ON resonance with the NO_2 $4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ [$R^*(4b_2)^{-1}$, ν_2'] vibrational levels with that obtained OFF resonance (Fig. 8a and b) shows a smaller relative intensity of the lowest NO^+ vibrational levels in the latter case. No bimodal rotational profiles are resolved for OFF resonance excitation.

FIG. 8. Kinetic energy release (KER) distribution of the NO^+ and O^- ion fragments (dots, black line) in region I (a) for $h\nu = 11.58$ eV (ON resonance) and (b) $h\nu = 11.62$ eV (OFF resonance), with $E_{\text{ext}} = 15$ V/cm. The spectra are fitted (red line) by a single series of Gaussian (black lines) of common width for each spectrum (170 meV for (a) and 200 meV for (b)), centered at the energies corresponding to the maxima of the observed NO^+ ($X^1\Sigma^+$, ν) vibrational peaks. Labels for vibrational levels are for $N = 0$.

In region II, the KER distribution shows the excitation of NO^+ vibrational levels from $\nu = 0$ up to $\nu = 5$ (Figure 9). Near the resonance (Fig. 9a) the broader peak FWHM (250 meV estimated by MC simulations) reflects a higher rotational excitation of the NO^+ fragment ($N_{\text{max}} \sim 30$) with a multimodal structure partially resolved for $\nu = 4$. Figures 9b and c report the KER spectra measured at the $h\nu = 12.24$ eV and 12.49 eV excitation energies selected for their correspondence with the four-photon excitation energies at wavelengths 405 nm and 397 nm studied previously⁹. The general shape of the spectra is similar to that of Fig. 9a, although at 12.24 eV the peak FWHM is narrower than at 12.41 eV and 12.49 eV, and a significant rotational excitation of the NO^+ ($^1\Sigma^+$, $\nu = 3$) level is observed. Figures 9b and c also display a comparison with the KER spectra obtained by four-photon excitation at wavelengths 405 nm and 397 nm, respectively. We note that spectral bandwidth is here of the order of 18 meV for the one-photon excitation, compared with a value up to 90 meV in the four-photon measurements⁹. Although their general shape is similar to that reported for one photon excitation in this region, some differences are observed, with e.g., a remarkable enhancement of the

NO^+ (${}^1\Sigma^+$, $\nu = 2$) for $\lambda = 397$ nm, to the expense of the NO^+ (${}^1\Sigma^+$, $\nu = 5$) level, in four-photon excitation scheme.

We note that similar vibrational and rotational profiles of the NO (${}^2\Pi_{1/2}$) molecular fragment produced by photodissociation of NO_2^* excited in the first and second electronic absorption bands lying about 3.2 eV and 5.1 eV above the NO_2 ground state have been observed previously^{1, 33, 34}. In these studies, rotational excitation of the molecular fragment was assigned to dissociation of bending excited states of the NO_2^* parent molecule, whereas vibrational excitation results a priori from N-O bond break *via* excitation of the symmetric stretching mode of NO_2^* . Both excitation transfer processes are likely to be favored by a coupling between a long lived excited state and a dissociative state of the parent molecule.

FIG. 9. Kinetic energy release (KER) distribution of the NO^+ and O^- ion fragments in region II for (a) $h\nu = 12.41$ eV (dots, black line, nearby a resonance), (b) for $h\nu = 12.24$ eV (dots, black line) corresponding to the 405 nm 4-photon excitation in ref 9 (triangles, blue line) and (c) for $h\nu = 12.49$ eV (dots, black line) corresponding to the 397 nm 4-photon excitation in ref 9 (triangles, blue line), with $E_{\text{ext}} = 24$ V/cm. In (b) and (c), the KER spectra are normalized such that both KER distribution integrals are equal. The spectrum in

(a) is fitted (red line) by a single series of Gaussian of common width (black line) (here 220 meV), centered at the energies corresponding to the maxima of the observed NO^+ ($X^1\Sigma^+$, ν) vibrational peaks. Labels for vibrational levels are for $N = 0$.

According to a similar scheme, the vibrational and rotational excitation of the NO^+ fragment observed ON resonance could be attributed to ion pair formation taking place *via* a coupling between the identified Rydberg states [$R^*(4b_2)^{-1}$, ν_2'] and e.g., the ion pair state, allowing an effective transfer of energy from the bending mode to the symmetric stretch mode. The outcome of such a coupling depends on the bending excitation level of the initial NO_2^* excited state^{33,34}. The strong vibrational excitation of the fragments could even be more strongly favored by the role of intermediate [$R^*(6a_1)^{-1}$] Rydberg states in high vibrational levels such as the one invoked in the discussion of Sec. IVC. Such a scheme has been suggested by Suits and Hepburn e.g., in the discussion of $\text{CH}_3^+ \text{-F}^-$ ion pair formation³¹. OFF resonance, the main characteristic of the KER spectra as illustrated in Figure 8b is the dominant excitation of the higher accessible vibrational state, here NO^+ ($^1\Sigma^+$, $\nu = 2$). Direct excitation from the bent ground state into the ion pair dissociative molecular state a priori requires the excitation of stretching modes of the parent molecule. This leads to the production of vibrationally excited molecular fragments, with an influence of the rotational excitation of the molecular fragment as a function of the bond angle of NO_2^* ³³.

B. Ion fragment angular distribution

The (KER, γ) bidimensional histogram in Figure 7 enables us to analyze the ion-fragment emission pattern with respect to the light polarization axis as a function of the vibrational state of the NO^+ ($^1\Sigma^+$, ν) fragment in the (NO^+ ($^1\Sigma^+$, ν) + O^2P) dissociation channel. The photofragment angular distribution is determined by the direction of the transition moment defined by the symmetries of the NO_2 initial and final states for a given geometry and it is characterized by an asymmetry

parameter β_N . Here we use the notation introduced in ref. 9, where type-1, type-2 and type-3 electronic transitions correspond to a transition moment in the molecular frame being perpendicular to the plane of the NO_2 molecule (\mathbf{t}_1), parallel to the line connecting the two O atoms (\mathbf{t}_2), or parallel to the C_{2v} symmetry axis (\mathbf{t}_3), respectively, as sketched in Figure 10a. For such well defined transitions, photofragment emission takes place in the plane of the molecule, in a direction perpendicular to the polarization axis (type-1), or almost parallel (type-2) or almost perpendicular (type-3) to the polarization axis, reflected by a value of β_N around -1, 1.5 and -0.5, respectively, for the NO_2 ground state geometry characterized by the $\angle\text{ONO}$ angle $\theta_{\text{eq}} = 133.85^\circ$ shown in Figure 10b. We note that, considering transition moments in the plane of a C_{2v} molecule such as NO_2 , in contrast with the characteristics of angular distributions of the recoil fragments for photoexcitation of a linear molecule, the “parallel” behavior of the recoil ion distribution with a positive β_N value corresponds to a transition between states of different symmetry, although the “perpendicular” behavior with a negative β_N value corresponds to a transition between states of same symmetry. If the $\angle\text{ONO}$ angle θ is different from θ_{eq} , a classical model assuming axial recoil fragmentation allows us to relate the β_N parameter to the equilibrium angle θ for each type of transition through the analytical expressions:

$$\beta = 2 - 3\cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \text{ for a type-2 transition} \quad (5)$$

and

$$\beta = -1 + 3\cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \text{ for a type-3 transition.} \quad (6)$$

In addition to the influence of a modified geometry of the molecule as described by Eq. 5 and 6, an asymmetry parameter pointing to other values than -1, 1.5 or -0.5, may be attributed to a superposition of transitions of different symmetries, or to the influence of rotation of the NO_2 parent molecule prior to dissociation, which may occur for long lived excited states³⁴⁻³⁷.

FIG. 10. Scheme of the NO₂ molecule: (a) transition moments \mathbf{t}_1 , \mathbf{t}_2 , \mathbf{t}_3 in the C_{2v} symmetry (b) axial recoil conditions for the ground state geometry NO₂ (X^2A_1) with $\theta_{\text{eq}} = 133.85^\circ$.

The results obtained for several excitation energies (ON and OFF resonance) in regions I and II are reported in Table I. Regarding region I ON resonance, the β_N values are positive, consistent with the dominant contribution of the $4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ (NO₂ (X^2A_1) \rightarrow 2B_2) type-2 transition identified in Sec. III. However significant variations are observed with (i) the initial ν_2' bending vibrational level of the NO₂ $4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ [$R^*(4b_2)^{-1}, \nu_2'$] Rydberg state and (ii) the ν vibrational state of the NO⁺ fragment. The measured β_N values for the two first excitation energies ($h\nu \approx 11.50$ eV and 11.58 eV) assigned to the resonances $4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ ($\nu_2' = 2$ and $\nu_2' = 3$) are very similar, decreasing from $\beta_N \approx 0.9$ ($\nu = 0$) to 0.4 ($\nu = 1-2$), whereas they are larger for the third resonance $4b_2 \rightarrow 4sa_1$ ($\nu_2' = 4$) ($h\nu \approx 11.66$ eV) varying from $\beta_N \approx 1.3$ ($\nu = 0$) to 0.4 ($\nu = 2$). When the excitation energy is OFF resonance ($h\nu \approx 11.62$ eV) β_N takes lower values between 0.4 ($\nu = 0$) and 0 ($\nu = 2$). For each excitation energy, β_N decreases significantly when the NO⁺ vibrational level increases, the dissociation channel being closer to resonance with the incident photon energy. Monte-Carlo simulations show that the instrumental widths do not account for this significant decrease even at the low KER values considered.

TABLE I. Asymmetry parameters β_N for $(\text{NO}^+, \text{O}^-)$ coincident events recorded for each vibrational level NO^+ ($^1\Sigma^+$, from $\nu = 0$ up to 5) as a function of the excitation energy in region I and II. Italic characters indicate excitation energy OFF resonance. Intermediate Rydberg states reached in region I are indicated (see Section III).

Excitation energy	NO_2^* Rydberg State	$\beta_N (\pm 0.05)$						
		$\nu = 0$	$\nu = 1$	$\nu = 2$	$\nu = 3$	$\nu = 4$	$\nu = 5$	
Region I	11.50	$4b_2 \rightarrow 4s_{a_1}$ ($\nu_2' = 2$)	0.9	0.4				
	11.58	$4b_2 \rightarrow 4s_{a_1}$ ($\nu_2' = 3$)	0.9	0.35	0.4			
	<i>11.62</i>		<i>0.4</i>	<i>0.15</i>	<i>0.05</i>			
	11.66	$4b_2 \rightarrow 4s_{a_1}$ ($\nu_2' = 4$)	1.3	0.85	0.4			
Region II	12.24		0.9	0.8	0.5	0.45	0.6	
	12.41		0.2	-0.2	-0.2	-0.2	-0.3	
	12.49		0.3	0.05	-0.2	-0.2	-0.45	

The largest anisotropy, with a β_N value close to the one expected for a type-2 transition ($\beta_N \approx 1.5$), is observed when the maximum internal energy of the NO_2 molecule is transferred into translational energy of the fragments i.e. for the dissociation channel ($\nu_2' = 4 \rightarrow \nu = 0$). A first interpretation of the β_N dependence can accordingly be related to the dissociation time τ_D , which varies inversely with the magnitude of the KER of the fragments.

For direct dissociation, τ_D estimated at a $(\text{NO}^+, \text{O}^-)$ distance of 10 a.u. assuming a purely dissociative state varies with the NO^+ fragment vibrational level between 0.4 ps for $\nu = 0$ and 1.34 ps for $\nu = 2$, remaining quite similar for ν_2' varying between 2 and 4 with $h\nu$. These values are of the same order of magnitude as the rotational period estimated around 2 ps for a rotation temperature of 100 K. Thus, the effect of NO_2 molecular rotation may result in a blurring of the angular distribution^{35, 36}, reflected by a reduced asymmetry parameter for $\nu = 2$. However, it cannot

explain the decrease in β_N measured for $h\nu$ corresponding to an initial vibrational excitation $v_2' = 2, 3$ compared to $v_2' = 4$.

The influence of the v_2' bending quantum number may be understood in terms of the coupling mechanism between the $[R^*(4b_2)^{-1}, v_2']$ excited state and the ion pair dissociative state invoked in the preceding Sec. VA, if e.g., the crossing geometry is significantly different for different v_2' states. The present results suggest that the coupling between the $4s$ $v_2' = 4$ level and the ion pair state occurs at a geometry closer to the equilibrium geometry than that of the $v_2' = 2-3$ states, resulting in a β_N asymmetry parameter closer to the 1.5 value corresponding to axial recoil, i.e., to a $\angle ONO$ angle $\theta = 133.4^\circ$. The lower β_N values measured for the $v_2' = 2-3$ states indicate a larger reduction in bond angle, consistent with the higher rotational excitation of the molecular fragment discussed in Sec. VA. Non axial recoil dynamics associated with a modification of the excited state geometry for NO_2 photodissociation has been reported earlier^{34,37}. Using eq.(5) accordingly, the $\angle ONO$ θ_c angles at the crossing geometry associated with the measured β_N values taken for the NO^+ ($^1\Sigma^+$, $v=0$), corresponding to the largest anisotropy for a given v_2' , vary from $\theta_c \approx 120^\circ$ (close to the equilibrium angle of the NO_2^+ (a^3B_2)) to $\theta_c \approx 104^\circ$ for $\beta_N = 1.3$ or 0.9 , respectively.

The significantly smaller values of β_N obtained OFF resonance in region I (Table I) may result from the direct excitation of the two molecular states of different symmetries B_2 and A_1 correlated to the ($NO^+ X^1\Sigma^+ v = 0$, $O^- ^2P_{3/2(1/2)}$) ion pair limits.

Regarding region II, extracting the asymmetry parameters for each NO^+ vibrational level is more difficult due to the broadness of the peaks in the KER spectrum. For $h\nu = 12.24$ eV, the β_N values reported in Table I vary from 0.9 to 0.45 similarly to those measured in region I, highlighting a similar dissociation dynamics. For $h\nu = 12.41$ eV and $h\nu = 12.49$ eV, near the observed resonances, the β_N values range from 0.4 to -0.45 for increasing vibrational levels (from $v = 0, 1$ up to $v = 5$). They are negative for the dominantly populated level $v = 3$ to $v = 5$, while positive values are found for lower vibrational excitation, with small differences for the two photon energies.

The dominant contribution of the higher vibrational levels ($v = 4$ and 5) associated with negative

values of β_N suggests the role of a type-3 ($A_1 \rightarrow A_1$) or type-1 ($A_1 \rightarrow B_1$) transition in this region, both consistent with the excitation of $[R^*(4b_2)^{-1}, \nu_2']$ Rydberg states following $4b_2 \rightarrow 4d$ and $5d$ excitation. The β_N values for lower vibrational states of NO^+ , remain weakly negative or positive, may involve the excitation of Rydberg series $4b_2 \rightarrow 5s_{a_1}$ and $4b_2 \rightarrow 6s_{a_1}$ (3B_2), consistent with the high density of Rydberg states populated in this region as discussed in Sec. III.

VI. CONCLUSION

We have reported a vector correlation method investigation of photoionization into the NO_2^+ ($X \ ^1\Sigma_g^+$) ground state and ($NO^+({}^1\Sigma^+) + O^-({}^2P)$) ion-pair formation induced by one photon excitation of the NO_2 molecule in the 10.9 -13 eV excitation energy range where both processes are observed simultaneously. The main goal of this study is to contribute to the understanding of the complex electron-nuclear photodynamics of NO_2 , in particular that induced in multiphoton absorption by femtosecond pulses at about 400 nm.

Although ion-pair production accounts for a minor channel after one photon absorption (about one percent of ionization), the ion yield spectra reported for both reactions exhibit remarkably similar structures in the explored photon energy range, which demonstrate the strong influence of vibrationally resolved $[R^*(4b_2)^{-1}, n\alpha_i, \nu_2']$ Rydberg states. Two regions have been selected for a more thorough study. In region I around 11.5 eV, the well resolved bending vibrationally excited levels of the $4s_{a_1}$ $[R^*(4b_2)^{-1}]$ Rydberg state enable us to perform a complete energy and angular analysis of the outcome of ionization and ion pair formation after excitation ON and OFF resonance with ν_2' bending modes. A similar level of information is reported for region II around 12.4 eV, corresponding to that reached after absorption of four 400 nm photons, although the density of $[R^*(4b_2)^{-1}, n\alpha_i, \nu_2']$ Rydberg series is higher.

Regarding photoionization, the measured photoelectron spectra and asymmetry parameters support the existence of two different binding energy regions. Photoionization into the NO_2^+ ($X \ ^1\Sigma_g^+, \nu$) ground state for E_B values lower than the $E_B^{(FC)}$ center of the FC region associated with the NO_2 (X

2A_1) ground state geometry, corresponding to $\angle\text{ONO}$ angle $\theta > \theta_{\text{eq}}$ equilibrium angle ($\theta_{\text{eq}} = 133.85^\circ$), displays fingerprints of direct ionization consistent with FCHF calculations, although significant deviations from the FC ionization probability as well as from the β_e evolution predicted by the FCHF calculations for direct ionization are observed for larger E_B values. This behavior may be attributed to a vibronic coupling influencing the ionization process for the higher vibrational levels of the NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g^+$) ionic state or vibronic coupling of NO_2^* states such as that induced by a conical intersection. On the other hand, autoionization ON resonance with prominent $[\text{R}^*(4b_2)^{-1}, \nu_2']$ Rydberg states reveals two competing mechanisms. In region I, autoionization of the $4sa_1$ $[\text{R}^*(4b_2)^{-1}, \nu_2'=4]$ state occurs in the FC region, even if deviations from the FC profile are observed, with a significant decrease of the photoelectron emission anisotropy compared with that of ionization OFF resonance. In region II, autoionization of $[\text{R}^*(4b_2)^{-1}, \nu_2']$ states outside the FC region leads mainly to threshold photoelectrons and production of highly excited vibrational states of NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g^+$), the weak β_e asymmetry parameter being comparable ON and OFF resonance. Calculations of potential energy surfaces suggest a coupling between $[\text{R}^*(4b_2)^{-1}, \nu_2']$ excited state and $[\text{R}^*(6a_1)^{-1}, \nu_2]$ Rydberg states converging to highly excited vibrational states of NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g^+$, ν), which may lead to vibrational or rotational autoionization that would produce threshold electrons. This mechanism should be favored for narrow linewidths of the $n\ell\alpha_i$ $[\text{R}^*(4b_2)^{-1}, \nu_2']$ Rydberg states.

Ion pair formation leads to a strong vibrational and rotational excitation of the NO^+ ($^1\Sigma^+$, ν) molecular fragment. This implies an effective coupling between the bending mode and the symmetric stretch mode of the NO_2^* molecule, which should be favored by the coupling between $[\text{R}^*(4b_2)^{-1}, \nu_2]$ Rydberg states populated ON resonance and the ion pair dissociation potential curve taking place e.g., at an avoided crossing. In region I, the rovibrational excitation of the NO^+ ($^1\Sigma^+$, $\nu = 0, 1, 2$) molecular product gives rise to bimodal rotational distributions similar to that observed in the investigation of other neutral channel dissociation of NO_2 ^{34, 37}. The positive β_N asymmetry parameter obtained for each vibrational state of the NO^+ ($^1\Sigma^+$, ν) fragment is primarily a fingerprint

of the dominant role of NO_2^* excited state of B_2 (A') symmetry correlated with the ion pair dissociation limit, enhanced for ON resonance excitation of the $4s_{a_1}$ [$R^*(4b_2)^{-1}, \nu_2'$] Rydberg states. The β_N variations, observed as a function of the ν_2' bending quantum number of the parent molecule and the ν vibrational level of the NO^+ fragment, may reflect the role of nuclear dynamics such as rotation of the NO_2 molecule prior to dissociation for low KERs, or a variation of the NO_2 excited state geometry characterized by the $\angle\text{ONO}$ angle and R_{NO} distance when dissociation occurs. The detailed interpretation of the energy sharing between the vibrational and rotational excitation modes and their consequence in terms of ion fragment emission anisotropies would require a more detailed model of such couplings and will be pursued in forthcoming molecular calculations.

In region II, the general behavior of the KER spectra is very similar to that observed after 400 nm 4-photon absorption⁹. Although more intense excitation of specific vibrational modes was also found, we conclude that most of the couplings leading to the rovibrational distribution of the fragments may be assigned to the molecular structure of the ionization continuum in the 12.4 eV binding energy region. In particular the role of [$R^*(4b_2)^{-1}, \nu_2$] Rydberg states and their possible coupling with [$R^*(6a_1)^{-1}$] Rydberg states influences both ionization into the NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g^+$) ground state and ($\text{NO}^+(^1\Sigma^+) + \text{O}^-(^2P)$) ion-pair formation. The negative β_N asymmetry parameter measured for the higher vibrational states of $\text{NO}^+(^1\Sigma^+)$ is assigned to the increasing role of NO_2^* molecular states of A_1 (A') or A_2 (A'') symmetry.

The reported results provide a ground for a parallel investigation of the role of Rydberg states in ultrafast multiphoton ionization of the NO_2 molecule, both experimentally and theoretically, and they should contribute to the interpretation of recoil frame photoemission observables at reach when dissociative ionization occurs. Further investigations using a femtosecond laser source tunable in the 380-420 nm range are in progress at SLIC-Saclay.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are very grateful to L. Nahon, DESIRS beamline director, G. Garcia, DESIRS beamline scientist (SOLEIL) for their cooperation, the machine department staff for operating SOLEIL, and E. Bouisset, S. Damoy (ISMO), and J. F. Gil (SOLEIL) for their technical support. D.D. and S.M.P thank L. Poisson for fruitful discussions and R. Cireasa for a careful reading of the manuscript. We are very grateful to J.C. Houver for the development of data analysis software for this research program and to N. Saquet for his participation to the experimental work. The support of the PICS (Programme international de cooperation scientifique CNRS No. 05460) and the Triangle de la Physique (DYNELEC No. 2008-046T) is gratefully acknowledged. R.R.L. acknowledges the support of the Chemical Sciences, Geosciences and Biosciences Division, Office of Basic Energy Sciences, Office of Science, U.S. Department of Energy and of the Robert A. Welch Foundation (Houston, TX) under Grant A-1020. The computational studies were performed at the Texas A&M University Supercomputing Facility and on facilities supported by the National Science Foundation (Grant No. CHE-0541587).

REFERENCES

- ¹I. Wilkinson, and J. Whitaker, *Annu. Rep. Prog. Chem. Sect. C* **106**, 1 (2010).
- ²N. T. Form, B. J. Whitaker, L. Poisson and B. Soep, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **8**, 2925 (2006).
- ³J. B. Hamard, R. Cireasa, B. Chatel, V. Blanchet and B. J. Whitaker, *J. Phys. Chem. A* **114**, 3167 (2010)
- ⁴J. A. Davies, R. E. Continetti, D. W. Chandler, C. C. Hayden, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **84**, 5983 (2000).
- ⁵A. Vredenburg, W. G. Roeterdink, M. H. M. Janssen, *J Chem. Phys.*, **128**, 204311 (2008).
- ⁶Y. Arasaki, K. Takatsuka, K. Wang, and V. McKoy, *J. Chem. Phys.* **132**, 124307 (2010).
- ⁷H. J. Wörner, J. B. Bertrand, B. Fabre, J. Higuët, H. Ruf, A. Dubrouil, S. Patchkovski, M. Spanner, Y. Mairesse, and V. Blanchet, *Science* **334**, 208 (2011).
- ⁸H. Ruf, C. Handshin, A. Ferré, N. Thiré, J. B. Bertrand, L. Bonnet, R. Cireasa, E. Constant, P. B.

- Corkum, D. Descamps, B. Fabre, P. Larregaray, E. Mével, S. Petit, B. Pons, D. Staedter, H. J. Wörner, D. M. Villeneuve, Y. Mairesse, P. Halvick and V. Blanchet, *J. Chem. Phys.* **137**, 224303 (2012).
- ⁹C. Elkharrat, Y. J. Picard, P. Billaud, C. Cornaggia, D Garzella, M. Perdrix, J. C. Houver, R. R. Lucchese, and D. Doweck, *J. Phys. Chem. A* **114**, 9902 (2010).
- ¹⁰A. Lafosse, M. Lebech, J. C. Brenot, P. M. Guyon, O. Jagutzki, L. Spielberger, M. Vervloet, J. C. Houver, and D. Doweck, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **84**, 5987 (2000).
- ¹¹M. Lebech, J. C. Houver, and D. Doweck, *Rev. of Sci. Instrum.* **73**, 1866 (2002).
- ¹² (a) J. Berkowitz, *VUV and Soft X-ray Photoionization* (ed. U. Becker and D.A. Shirley, Plenum Press, New York, 1996) Chapter 8 p. 263.(b) M. Kratzat, Ph.D.thesis, Freie Universität Berlin, 1984.
- ¹³V. H. Dibeler, J. A. Walker, and S. K. Liston, *J. of Research of the NBS-A Phys. and Chem.* **71A**, 37 (1967).
- ¹⁴P. Baltzer, L. Karlsson, B. Wannberg, D. M. P. Holland, M. A. MacDonald, M. A. Hayes, and J. H. D. Eland, *Chem. Phys.* **237**, 451 (1998).
- ¹⁵J. H. D. Eland, L. Karlsson, *Chem. Phys.* **237** 139 (1998).
- ¹⁶M. Richard-Viard, A. Delboubé, and M. Vervloet, *Chem. Phys.* **209**, 159 (1996).
- ¹⁷L. Nahon, N. de Oliveira, G. A. Garcia, J. F. Gil, B. Pilette, O. Marcouillé, B. Lagarde and F. Polack, *J. Synchrotron Rad.* **19**, 508 (2012).
- ¹⁸B. Mercier, M. Compin, C. Prevost, G. Bellec, R. Thissen, O. Dutuit, and L. Nahon, *J. Vac. Sci. Tech. A* **18**, 2533 (2000).
- ¹⁹DTPI: Détection: Temps, Position, Image; Technology Division of LUMAT (Federation FR2764, University Paris Sud and CNRS)
- ²⁰Y. Morioka, H. Masuko, M. Nakamura, M. Sasanuma, and E. Ishiguro, *Can. J. Phys.* **56(7)**, 962 (1978).
- ²¹G. K. Jarvis, Y. Song, C. Y. Ng, and E. R. Grant, *J. Chem. Phys.* **111**, 9568 (1999).

- ²²G. Herzberg, *Electronic Spectra and Electronic Structure of Polyatomic Molecules, Molecular Spectra and Molecular Structure Vol. III* (Van Nostrand Reinhold, New York, 1966).
- ²³F. A. Gianturco, R. R. Lucchese, and N. J. Sanna, *J. Chem. Phys.* **100**, 6464 (1994).
- ²⁴A. P. P. Natalense, and R. R. Lucchese, *J. Chem. Phys.* **111**, 5344 (1999).
- ²⁵R. A. Kendall, T. H. Dunning, and R. J. Harrison, *J. Chem. Phys.* **96**, 6796 (1992).
- ²⁶T. H. Dunning, *J. Chem. Phys.* **90**, 1007 (1989).
- ²⁷E. D. Poliakoff and R R Lucchese, *Phys. Scr.* **74**, C71 (2006).
- ²⁸ P. M. Guyon, T. Baer, and I. Nenner, *J. Chem. Phys.* **78**, 3665 (1983).
- ²⁹W. Chupka, P. J. Miller, and E. E. Eyler, *J. Chem. Phys.* **88**, 3032 (1988).
- ³⁰H. J. Werner, P. J. Knowles, R. Lindh, M. Schutz, P. Celani, T. Korona, F. R. Manby, G. Rauhut, R. D. Amos, A. Bernhardsson, A. Berning, D. L. Cooper, M. J. O. Deegan, A. J. Dobbyn, F. Eckert, C. Hampel, G. Hetzer, A. W. Lloyd, S. J. McNicholas, W. Meyer, M. E. Mura, A. Nicklass, P. Palmieri, R. Pitzer, U. Schumann, H. Stoll, A. J. Stone, R. Tarroni, and T. Thorsteinsson, MOLPRO, a package of ab initio programs (Birmingham, UK, 2003).
- ³¹A. G. Suits and J. W. Hepburn, *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.* **57**, 431 (2006).
- ³²K. P. Huber and G. Herzberg, *Constants of Diatomic Molecules, Molecular Spectra and Molecular Structure Vol IV* (Van Nostrand Reinhold, New York, 1979).
- ³³R. Schinke, *Photodissociation Dynamics* (Cambridge University Press, 1993).
- ³⁴I. Wilkinson, M. de Miranda, and B. J. Whitaker, *J. Chem. Phys.* **131**, 054308 (2009).
- ³⁵C. Jonah, *J. Chem. Phys.* **55**, 1915 (1971).
- ³⁶S. Yang, and R. Bersohn, *J. Chem. Phys.* **61**, 4400 (1974).
- ³⁷A. V. Demyanenko, V. Dribinski, H. Reisler, H. Meyer, and C. X. W. Qian, *J. Chem. Phys.* **111**, 7383 (1999).